

Embracing Human-Centered Leadership in Sterile Processing: A Path to Excellence

BY JUAN MIGUEL RAMOS, REGIONAL DIRECTOR OF STERILE PROCESSING—ASCENSION HEALTH

In the rapidly evolving healthcare landscape, effective leadership is the cornerstone that drives departmental effectiveness, efficiency and morale. The stakes are incredibly high within the Sterile Processing (SP) profession, where precision, compliance and safety are paramount. As outlined in *Human-Centered Leadership in Healthcare* by Kay Kennedy, Lucy Leclerc and Susan Campis, the principles of human-centered leadership offer a transformative approach that can revolutionize operations and outcomes.

This article explores how human-centered leadership principles can be integrated into the SP environment to engage executives, managers, technicians and support staff in a shared vision of excellence.

Essence of human-centered leadership

Kennedy, Leclerc and Campis define human-centered leadership as prioritizing people's welfare, advancement and empowerment to achieve organizational objectives. This leadership style moves beyond traditional top-down management practices to foster environments where every team member feels valued,

understood and motivated to contribute their best. Adopting this leadership style for Sterile Processing departments (SPDs) can lead to improved employee satisfaction, reduced turnover, enhanced compliance and, ultimately, better patient outcomes.

SPDs hold a unique position within healthcare systems—operating behind the scenes to ensure surgical instruments and medical devices are properly cleaned, disinfected, inspected, assembled and sterilized for safe use on patients. The pressure to adhere to strict standards, meet demanding timelines and manage complex workflows is immense; however, the broader healthcare system frequently underappreciates the critical nature of SP professionals' work. This disconnect can lead to frustration and burnout among SP professionals; therefore, leaders must cultivate a culture of respect, recognition and collaboration.

Applying human-centered leadership effectively in the SPD requires targeted steps that include:

Building trust with empathy—

Empathy is essential for providing human-centered leadership. In the SPD, where work is both highly technical and repetitive, leaders must take the time to understand their employees' challenges. Managers who actively

listen to technicians' concerns can build trust and foster an environment where employees feel comfortable sharing ideas and feedback.

Actionable example—Leaders can provide regular employee check-in sessions that focus on well-being and professional development. These sessions can identify stressors or barriers employees are facing so leaders and employees can work collaboratively to find appropriate solutions.

Encouraging autonomy—

Empowerment in the workplace is valuable because it gives employees the freedom to make decisions within their areas of expertise. In SPDs, this could involve allowing technicians to have a say in process improvements or equipment selection, enhancing their job satisfaction and contributing to greater operational effectiveness.

Actionable example—Leaders can benefit by establishing a cross-functional team that includes technicians, supervisors and quality assurance staff to evaluate and recommend changes to workflow or equipment. Ensuring the team's recommendations are considered and implemented where feasible is essential.

Creating a culture of appreciation—

Recognizing SP professionals' contributions is vital. Whether acknowledging a technician's meticulous attention to detail or celebrating a team's successful audit, regular recognition fosters a positive work environment and motivates continued excellence.

Actionable example—Consider creating an Employee of the Month program, highlighting individuals' specific patient safety or process efficiency contributions. Celebrate these achievements in staff meetings, newsletters and other forms of organizational communications.

Investing in growth—

Human-centered leaders understand that continuous learning is essential for individual and organizational success. For SPDs, this means providing ongoing education on the latest standards, technologies and best practices and ensuring opportunities for career advancement through mentorship and leadership development programs.

Actionable example—Partner with professional organizations, such as the Healthcare Sterile Processing Association (HSPA), to offer certifications and training programs. Encourage staff to attend conferences and workshops and provide financial support for these activities.

Supporting mental and physical

health—SP professionals' demanding roles can be physically and mentally taxing. Leaders must prioritize their employees' well-being by promoting work-life balance, offering support resources, and creating a culture where employee health is a priority.

Actionable example—Introduce wellness initiatives, such as onsite stress management workshops, access to counseling services, and flexible

scheduling options, to help employees manage their personal and professional responsibilities more effectively.

Conclusion

Human-centered leadership is not just a management strategy but a philosophy that places people at the center of organizational success. This type of leadership approach in the SPD can create a ripple effect beyond the department's walls. When SP professionals feel valued, empowered and supported, their commitment to excellence naturally increases. This, in turn, ensures that surgical instruments and medical devices are processed to the highest standards, directly contributing to improved patient safety and positive clinical outcomes.

As the industry advances, there is a collective need to lead with empathy, empower teams, and foster a culture of continuous improvement. SP leaders who embrace human-centered leadership will be better poised to transform operations, contributing to higher employee satisfaction, improved performance and better patient outcomes. At the same time, the leadership approach will help SP professionals strengthen their compliance with industry standards and thrive in a department where every team member feels valued and motivated to contribute to collective success. **P**

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Kennedy, K, Leclerc, L, and Campis, S. *Human-Centered Leadership in Healthcare: Evolution of a Revolution*. 2021.

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